

Community pharmacists' perceptions towards independent prescribing in Iraq: a qualitative study

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Received 22 December 2025 ♦ Accepted 30 April 2026 ♦ Published 21 May 2026

Citation: Al-Hamadani FY, Jasim AL, Saihood AH, Jawad SAK, Jabbar MM, Fawzi HA, Alhamdani FY (2026) Community pharmacists' perceptions towards independent prescribing in Iraq: a qualitative study. *Pharmacia* 73: e183314. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e183314>

Abstract

The role of pharmacists has evolved beyond traditional dispensing to encompass clinical and patient-centered activities, including medicine optimization, health promotion, and independent prescribing. Community pharmacists, often the first point of contact for healthcare advice, are well positioned to support healthcare systems through the development of prescribing roles. This qualitative study explored the attitudes of community pharmacists in Iraq toward the implementation of independent prescribing and its potential impact on patient care and healthcare delivery. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 10 community pharmacists. Thematic analysis indicated broad support for independent prescribing, particularly for the management of uncomplicated conditions. Perceived benefits included improved patient access to care, reduced waiting times, cost savings, and decreased workload for physicians. However, several challenges were identified, including limited clinical training, resistance from physicians, a lack of clear regulatory frameworks, and variability in community pharmacy infrastructure. Overall, community pharmacists viewed independent prescribing positively, recognizing its potential as a significant advancement and an opportunity to enhance healthcare delivery in Iraq.

Keywords

Community pharmacy services, drug, health knowledge, Iraq, pharmacists, prescribing

Introduction

It has long been acknowledged that the pharmacist's role has evolved beyond general dispensing to encompass

clinical and patient-centered care (Mugada et al. 2021; Ambusaidi et al. 2022). A key component of this evolution, particularly in high-income countries (HICs), is the development of independent prescribing (IP) (Abdelfatah

et al. 2024a). Independent prescribing allows pharmacists to take responsibility for prescribing medicines within their scope of competence, without prior approval from a physician. This shift is driven by the need to optimize healthcare resources, improve patient access to services, and enhance medication management across healthcare systems (Song et al. 2022). The concept is gaining traction in HICs such as the UK, Australia, Canada, and the USA, where studies have demonstrated generally favorable attitudes toward expanding the role of community pharmacists within healthcare systems (Kooner et al. 2020; Girvin et al. 2023; Grant et al. 2023).

UK-based research on pharmacist independent prescribing has shown that qualified independent prescribers report higher levels of job satisfaction (Mantzourani et al. 2023). Independent prescribing has also been associated with enhanced professional status for pharmacists, reduced workload pressures for general practitioners (GPs), and improved patient access to care (Abdelfatah et al. 2024b; Alghamdi 2024). Furthermore, a growing body of literature suggests that pharmacists are well suited to this role, given their extensive knowledge of pharmacology and accessibility. For example, Ramos et al. (2022), in a systematic review, found that positive perceptions of pharmacist prescribing were often linked to practitioners' knowledge and experience.

Global awareness of pharmacist independent prescribing is increasing, with growing research exploring its implementation and quality assurance issues that are particularly relevant for current and future healthcare development in Iraq. The Iraqi healthcare system continues to face significant challenges, particularly regarding access to primary care services (Agomo et al. 2018; Hamid et al. 2018). Consequently, patients often seek medical advice from community pharmacists as their first point of contact. This positions pharmacists as highly accessible healthcare providers and highlights the potential importance of independent prescribing in further expanding their role. However, this shift also has implications for pharmacists' responsibilities and raises questions about the feasibility of implementing such services within the existing educational and regulatory infrastructure (Nassir et al. 2024).

Even in Iraq, independent prescribing by community pharmacists is still an emerging concept. Most existing literature focuses on medication delivery in the absence of formal regulation, which is not consistent with a regulated and legal prescribing process. For example, a qualitative study conducted in 2020 on the unregulated use of antibiotics showed a negative image of such practices and recommended regulatory oversight (Alkadhimi et al. 2020). Many studies have also addressed the widespread dispensing of antimicrobial medications without prescriptions (Alkadhimi et al. 2024; Kadhim and Shanani 2025). In addition, one study examined the prescribing of nutritional supplements by pharmacists as another common example of unregulated independent prescribing practices in the country (Al-Hadi and Mikhael 2024). The research question—what are Iraqi community pharmacists' knowledge

of, attitudes toward, and perceptions of the practice of writing prescriptions for individual patients independently and the obstacles they encounter—must therefore be addressed so that this key area of practice may become more widely practiced. This qualitative study aims to explore the views of Iraqi community pharmacists on various aspects of independent prescribing.

Independent prescribing by community pharmacists in Iraq remains an emerging concept. Much of the existing literature focuses on medication supply in the absence of formal regulation, which differs considerably from a structured and legally regulated prescribing model. For example, a qualitative study conducted in 2020 on unregulated antibiotic use highlighted concerns about such practices and recommended stronger regulatory oversight (Alkadhimi et al. 2020). Other studies have also reported the widespread dispensing of antimicrobial medicines without prescriptions (Alkadhimi et al. 2024; Kadhim and Shanani 2025). In addition, one study examined the prescribing of nutritional supplements by pharmacists as another example of unregulated prescribing practices in the country (Al-Hadi and Mikhael 2024).

Given these gaps, it is important to explore Iraqi community pharmacists' knowledge of, attitudes toward, and perceptions of independent prescribing, as well as the barriers they encounter. Addressing these issues is essential to support the development and wider implementation of this key area of practice. This qualitative study therefore aims to explore the views of Iraqi community pharmacists on various aspects of independent prescribing.

Method

Study design

The study adopted a qualitative research design, using semi-structured interviews to explore community pharmacists' views on independent prescribing in Iraq. Qualitative approaches are particularly appropriate for examining complex phenomena from participants' perspectives and generating rich, contextualized insights (Braun and Clarke 2006).

Participants and recruitment

A purposive sampling strategy was employed to recruit 10 community pharmacists. Rather than aiming for statistical representativeness, participants were intentionally selected to capture a heterogeneous range of perspectives. Variation was sought in terms of age, years of professional experience, level of education (bachelor's vs. master's degree; public vs. private institutions), and employment status (pharmacy owner vs. employed pharmacist). Participants were required to be practicing community pharmacists currently working in Iraq.

To recruit participants, one of the authors visited community pharmacies across various geographical areas and distributed printed flyers outlining the purpose of the study and

providing contact details. This approach allowed pharmacists to express their interest voluntarily and privately.

The sample size was determined based on the principle of data saturation. Recruitment and interviews were completed after 10 participants, as analysis indicated that thematic saturation had been reached and no new conceptual themes were emerging from the data.

Data collection

One-to-one semi-structured interviews were conducted by the research team to collect data. The interview guide consisted of open-ended questions exploring pharmacists' current roles, knowledge of independent prescribing, perceived benefits and barriers, and key requirements for implementation (Alhamdani 2024). With participants' consent, interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim for subsequent analysis.

Data analysis

Key data were extracted from the interviews and shared with the research team for review. A detailed thematic analysis was undertaken to identify patterns (themes) within the data. The findings were coherent and provided clear explanations, enabling rigorous comparison and interpretation (Guest et al. 2011). The analytical process involved the following stages:

1. **Familiarization:** Repeated reading of transcripts to achieve immersion in the data.
2. **Initial coding:** Generating preliminary codes from the data to capture relevant features related to the research question.
3. **Theme development:** Grouping initial codes into higher-order themes.
4. **Analyzing themes:** Assessing whether the themes accurately reflected the coded data and the dataset as a whole.
5. **Defining and naming themes:** Refining themes to clearly define their scope and underlying meaning. Through this iterative process, six overarching themes and their associated codes were identified, as presented in Table 2.

Ethical approval

This study was approved by the Scientific and Ethical Committee of the College of Pharmacy at the University of Baghdad (approval number: RECAUBCP 1562024112R). Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their enrollment in the study.

Results

The research team conducted 10 interviews with community pharmacists. Of the participants, nine were male and

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of participating pharmacists ($n = 10$).

Characteristic	Category	Number
Age range (years)	25–30	2
	31–40	6
	41–50	2
Sex	Male	9
	Female	1
College of graduation	Public	7
	Private	3
Qualification level	Bachelor's degree	6
	Master's degree	4
Years of experience	1–5	3
	6–10	3
	>10	4
Pharmacy position	Proprietor	8
	Employed pharmacist	2

one was female. The demographic characteristics of the respondents are summarized in Table 1.

Thematic analysis of the interview data identified six major themes reflecting community pharmacists' perceptions of independent prescribing in Iraq. A thematic map summarizing these themes, associated sub-codes, and their interrelationships is presented in Fig. 1.

1. Pharmacist knowledge and awareness about health problems.
2. Pharmacists working as independent prescribers.
3. Diseases and conditions that can be managed by pharmacists as independent prescribers.
4. Impacts of independent prescribing.
5. Potential barriers to implementing independent prescribing.
6. Requirements for implementation of independent prescribing.

Theme 1: Pharmacist's knowledge and awareness of health problems

This theme comprised two sub-codes: the current level of knowledge and awareness among practicing pharmacists and the factors influencing this knowledge. Most participants believed that newly graduated pharmacists have lower levels of awareness and experience compared to their more senior counterparts. This was attributed to several factors, including the increasing number of pharmacy graduates and the expansion of private educational colleges and institutions. As Participant 3 explained:

“Each generation of pharmacists comes with fewer years and experiences than the previous generation. The reason why is because there is a huge population of pharmacists and private colleges which admit poor students. The knowledge is poor, particularly in externally educated graduates. The older generation is better and has better experience.”

Figure 1. Thematic map illustrating community pharmacists' perceptions of independent prescribing in Iraq. The diagram presents the key themes, associated sub-codes, and their interrelationships identified through qualitative analysis.

Conversely, some pharmacists highlighted additional factors, including a shift in attitudes compared to previous generations. Many younger pharmacists were perceived to be more interested in careers within the pharmaceutical industry, particularly in marketing and sales.

"I think pharmacists' knowledge is good, about 80% overall. However, previous graduates were better because they were a generation that knew they had to prepare themselves scientifically. But the current generation is preparing itself for marketing, so their thinking is different." Participant 5

"In my opinion, most pharmacists don't like to work in pharmacies and dispense medication. Most of them are headed in a different direction, which is pharmaceutical marketing. For example, a pharmacist may specialize in a specific area, such as cardiology, and have strong knowledge in that area, but not in other areas, as they focus their time and expertise on a specific area to be well-prepared when interacting with doctors." Participant 2

The ranking and type of academic institutions, particularly private colleges, were also cited as contributing to limited knowledge, especially regarding disease states.

"I think graduates from private colleges and abroad have weak information and very limited knowledge, but government graduates are better because the determining factor is the type of education," Participant 8.

Theme 2: Pharmacists working as independent prescribers

The concept of independent prescribing was introduced to participating pharmacists to explore their perspectives on the topic and its potential implementation in Iraq. Overall, most pharmacists expressed support for independent pre-

scribing, viewing it as a novel and promising initiative that could be successfully implemented with clear guidelines and regulatory frameworks in place.

As Participant 1 stated:

"If there's a role and guideline for it, but it shouldn't be done randomly."

"They emphasized the importance of pharmacists adhering to existing laws and not overstepping their boundaries into specialist medical diagnoses".

"I support its implementation if there's a role and guideline for it, but it shouldn't be done randomly if the pharmacist is well aware of a specific condition but isn't allowed to prescribe certain medications according to existing laws, such as blood pressure or heart medications that require a diagnosis or differential diagnosis, or cases that necessitate a full diagnosis by a specialist. It's not logical for a patient with hypertension to visit an orthopaedic doctor and expect to get a prescription for blood pressure medication. Pharmacists should adhere to existing laws and not interfere with the doctor's role, as per current regulations in Iraq." Participant 1

Some pharmacists viewed independent prescribing as an opportunity to expand their professional roles and enhance the function of community pharmacies, with the potential to increase patient engagement (Participant 4).

"My opinion is that the field has immense potential; pharmacies are facing limited opportunities. Having specialized pharmacists who can diagnose means pharmacies can pull in more patients." Participant 4

There was consensus that independent prescribing should be limited to appropriately selected, less complex cases and that pharmacists must have sufficient experience and engage in continuous professional development to remain up to date with evolving scientific knowledge (Participants 5, 9).

“The concept is transferable, but the pharmacist needs to be kept informed on a continuing basis. Pharmacists would need to carry that same qualifications and be kept up to date. Doctors, for example, go to one or three conferences annually to be up-to-date on the latest recommendations in their field, so pharmacists would have comparable qualifications and must keep up with the current updates.” Participant 5

“It’s a good idea but it has to be in very narrow and very specific regions, not for all cases,” Participant 9.

Theme 3: Diseases and conditions considered appropriate for pharmacist independent prescribing

In this study, participating pharmacists were asked to identify the types of conditions that could be managed under independent prescribing. The focus was on conditions beyond those typically treated with over-the-counter (OTC) medicines.

Overall, pharmacists agreed that independent prescribing should be limited to less complex conditions that may not require referral to a physician. Examples included uncomplicated infections, such as urinary tract infections, respiratory tract infections, and gastrointestinal infections, as well as certain dermatological conditions (e.g., eczema and fungal infections) and some musculoskeletal or pain-related conditions.

Conversely, pharmacists identified several conditions as being beyond their current or anticipated scope of practice and more appropriately managed by specialist physicians. These included chronic diseases, such as diabetes, cardiovascular conditions, central nervous system (CNS) disorders, and ophthalmic conditions. As noted by Participant 2, pharmacists felt more confident managing common acute conditions, particularly gastrointestinal and respiratory issues, due to their familiarity with the associated medications. However, they expressed lower confidence in managing chronic or more complex conditions.

“Our pharmacists know more about the drugs they typically prescribe at pharmacies, like those for gastrointestinal and respiratory problems, and antibiotics. However, their knowledge of medications of diabetes and CNS disorders is usually low, at around 20 percent; this is because they tend so often to be less likely to be offered in common prescription medicine. Contrary to pharmaceuticals which are often found in pharmacies on day-to-day basis in the usual list.” Participant 2

Participants 3 and 8 emphasized that complex or chronic conditions, particularly those requiring an initial diagnosis, fall beyond the typical scope of pharmacy practice. They further suggested that even pharmacists with postgraduate qualifications may need to consult physicians in certain cases.

“Pharmacists can manage antifungal cases for infections on the scalp and body, but chronic and complex cases are beyond their scope. These cases may require pharmacists with advanced degrees, such as master’s or Ph.D., and even then, it’s essential to consult a physician.” Participant 3

“I anticipate that pharmacists can manage cases like viral and bacterial infections, urinary tract infections, and simple skin conditions. However, more complex cases, such as heart failure, hypertension, and diabetes, might be more challenging to guarantee.” Participant 8

“I think cases of pain management, such as osteoarthritis (OA), but the problem arises with how pharmacists can make a diagnosis. Additionally, cases that have been previously diagnosed with diseases requiring follow-up, like a patient diagnosed with diabetes mellitus (DM), are manageable. However, initial diagnosis is challenging; pharmacists are better suited for cases that require simple diagnosis and monitoring,” Participant 9.

Theme 4: Impacts of independent prescribing

The impact of pharmacist independent prescribing in Iraq is complex and cannot be predicted based on a single condition. Drawing on participants’ perspectives, the anticipated impacts of independent prescribing were grouped into three main categories: effects on patients, the health-care system, and pharmacists (see Table 2).

Impact of independent prescribing on patients

Pharmacists expressed generally positive views regarding the anticipated impact of IP on patient care, while also acknowledging certain challenges. Commonly identified benefits included:

1. Financial savings—Independent prescribing may reduce patients’ healthcare expenses, particularly by minimizing the need for physician consultations.
2. Time efficiency—IP could save patients time by reducing the need to visit a doctor.
3. Reduced treatment delays—by decreasing waiting times for physician appointments, IP may enable more timely treatment and help prevent the progression of medical conditions.
4. Improved accessibility and convenience of care—pharmacists are often more accessible than physicians, and in Iraq, consultations are typically free of charge, making healthcare more accessible to a wider population.

“From my perspective, the benefits are that we save patients who can’t afford doctors’ fees, reduce their financial burden, and spare them the effort and wait time for appointments that can take 3 to 6 months.” Participant 2

Table 2. Study themes and associated codes.

Themes	Codes
Pharmacists' knowledge and awareness of health problems	1. Level of knowledge and awareness among pharmacists in pharmacy practice 2. Factors affecting pharmacists' knowledge and awareness
Pharmacists working as independent prescribers	1. Acceptance of pharmacists as independent prescribers 2. Pharmacists' attitudes toward independent prescribing 3. Requirements for pharmacists to become independent prescribers
Diseases and conditions that can be managed by pharmacists as independent prescribers	1. Types of diseases 2. Severity of diseases 3. Diseases and conditions that pharmacists are unable to manage.
Impacts of independent prescribing	1. The impact of independent prescribing on patients 2. The impact of independent prescribing on the healthcare system 3. The impact of independent prescribing on pharmacists
Potential barriers to implementing independent prescribing	1. Institutional- and professional-related barriers 2. Pharmacist-related barriers
Requirements for the implementation of independent prescribing	1. Pharmacist competence 2. Resources required for implementing independent prescribing 3. Regulatory support to facilitate the implementation of independent prescribing 4. Institutional adoption of independent prescribing 5. Responsible authorities for training & monitoring 6. Pharmacists after the implementation of independent prescribing

"I think the positive aspect for the patient in Iraq is that, most importantly, it's cost-effective since it's implemented in pharmacies without any fees. This provides a financial benefit. The second benefit is time-saving, as there's no waiting for appointments. Another important point is that doctors are not available 24/7, whereas pharmacists are always available. From a scientific perspective, pharmacists are more knowledgeable about medications, especially when new drugs are introduced, so that they can prescribe the best option for the patient." Participant 5

"In my opinion, the cost of treatment is lower, and the time to receive treatment is faster, allowing patients to get treated more quickly. Many patients often delay or struggle to visit a doctor, so this could help them get treated faster." Participant 7

"It's multifactorial, but I expect there will definitely be a positive impact when the patient receives information from a certified person." Participant 10

However, pharmacists also highlighted several potential risks associated with independent prescribing for patients, including the following concerns:

- **Insufficient clinical knowledge:** There is a risk of adverse outcomes if pharmacists lack the necessary clinical expertise (Participant 4).
- **Diagnostic errors:** Misdiagnosis may lead to inappropriate treatment and potential medication misuse (Participant 6).
- **Failure to refer:** Some pharmacists may not appropriately refer complex or high-risk cases to physicians when required (Participant 6).
- **Overprescribing or inappropriate antibiotic use:** Without adequate antimicrobial stewardship and regulatory oversight, there is a risk of overprescribing and misuse of antibiotics (Participant 7).
- **Scope creep:** Pharmacists may extend beyond their scope of competence, for example, by managing chronic conditions or undertaking minor medical procedures without appropriate training (Participant 8).

"The negatives depend on the pharmacist's knowledge and expertise. If the pharmacist possesses the necessary scientific knowledge and can accurately diagnose, there will be no negativity. The negative aspect arises when they misdiagnose or prescribe incorrect treatment." Participant 4

"I think the negative consequences for the patient may arise if the case is beyond the pharmacist's expertise or if it's a complex case and the pharmacist doesn't refer it, the pharmacist's treatment and diagnosis may be incorrect, leading to medication errors." Participant 6

"There's a risk of antibiotic misuse if pharmacists prescribe them inappropriately." Participant 7

"There's a possibility of misuse, and pharmacists might prescribe medications for chronic cases, and possibly even perform minor procedures." Participant 8.

Impact of independent prescribing on the health care system

Based on feedback from participating pharmacists, the potential benefits of implementing IP within the health-care system include:

1. Reduced workload for doctors and hospitals: Pharmacists managing appropriate cases may help alleviate pressure on overstretched health-care services.
2. Improved system efficiency: IP may enhance operational efficiency within healthcare settings, thereby enhancing care coordination between doctors and pharmacists.
3. Better allocation of healthcare resources: Managing less complex cases in the community could reduce system pressures and enable physicians to prioritize more serious or urgent conditions.
4. Optimized medicine use and safety: IP may support safer and more appropriate use of medicines, including reducing the risk of inappropriate antibiotic prescribing.

As highlighted by one participant:

“Pharmacists can help reduce hospital workload by taking on more responsibility for minor cases that do not require referral. If pharmacists are well-trained and experienced, they can manage non-severe cases. This can reduce the workload in emergency or consultation departments, as many patients present with minor issues that take up doctors’ time. This can optimise the healthcare system.” (Participant 1)

“The benefits to the healthcare system include saving time. Instead of going to the doctor, then to the lab, and finally to the pharmacy, patients can visit the pharmacy directly, saving time and money. Secondly, it will enhance coordination between doctors and pharmacists, thereby improving their strained relationship. It will become more collaborative, rather than each profession working in isolation. Additionally, IP will reduce doctors’ financial ties to pharmacies and the practice of prescribing drugs that benefit their own interests. It will also reduce the trend of doctors owning pharmacies and passing them down to their family members.” Participant 2

“It benefits by potentially controlling drug-drug interactions and also controlling the misuse of antibiotics.” Participant 7

“The advantage is alleviating the burden on hospitals and care centers by identifying patients who can afford to pay for services. This enables us to differentiate between those who can afford to pay for pharmacist services, which are typically less expensive than a doctor’s consultation.” Participant 10

One participant expressed a contrasting view, suggesting that implementing independent prescribing without appropriate regulation would not benefit the healthcare system or support medical professionals.

“There won’t be any benefits because in Iraq, we won’t be able to control pharmacists. They might still intervene in emergency cases, prescribing medications like nitroglycerin, Clexane, and Xarelto tablets. These are specialized medications that should only be prescribed by a specialist doctor. This wouldn’t have a positive impact on any level, including for doctors, as pharmacists wouldn’t be seen as qualified prescribers compared to a doctor who has completed 8 years of specialization, especially for the chronic diseases,” Participant 3.

Impact of independent prescribing on pharmacists

Participating pharmacists identified several potential benefits of implementing independent prescribing in Iraq, many of which would directly benefit pharmacists and contribute to the advancement of the pharmacy profession. These perceived benefits include:

1. Enhancing scientific and clinical knowledge, experience, and ongoing professional development among pharmacists.
2. Creating new career pathways and employment opportunities, helping to better structure the growing pharmacy workforce.
3. Elevating the professional status of pharmacists in society and strengthening public trust in their expertise.
4. Providing potential financial benefits, including increased revenue for community pharmacies.

“Firstly, it will increase his (pharmacist) status in the pharmacy and increase people’s trust in him (pharmacist). If pharmacists are allowed to dispense and prescribe under this system, they will be seen as knowledgeable and scientifically grounded. Secondly, there is a financial incentive for pharmacists, as the pharmacy’s income will increase, and even if a pharmacist is present, their salary might increase.” Participant 2

“Independent prescribing would create job opportunities for pharmacists and motivate them to seek out opportunities. Furthermore, non-scientific pharmacists will be compelled to become knowledgeable, as they would be embarrassed if someone asked them questions and they didn’t know the answers. This increases their status in society, and they will play a contributing and active role.” Participant 5

“Managing the large numbers of pharmacists and benefiting from them could lead to new roles for pharmacists, increasing their involvement and the Ministry of Health’s reliance on them and need, and certainly, there will be financial benefits for pharmacists.” Participant 8.

Theme 5: Potential barriers to implementing independent prescribing

If independent prescribing is implemented in Iraq, it is likely to face both institutional and professional barriers that may hinder its adoption. Identifying effective strategies to address these challenges is therefore essential. Based on participants’ perspectives, these barriers can be broadly categorized as institutional or pharmacist-related. Key concerns include:

1. Resistance from physicians, who may be reluctant to accept an expanded clinical role for pharmacists in patient care and decision-making.
2. Limited clinical training and expertise, with concerns that some pharmacists may not be adequately prepared to assess or manage certain clinical conditions.
3. Ministerial and bureaucratic challenges, including difficulties in obtaining formal approval for the implementation of independent prescribing.
4. Lack of clear legal and regulatory frameworks, particularly regarding pharmacists’ authority to prescribe beyond OTC medicines.

5. Unlike primary care or medical clinic settings, current pharmacy layouts may not support effective patient communication or private consultations.
6. Limited capacity for clinical assessment, including the inability to conduct physical examinations or access diagnostic investigations, which are often required for managing more complex cases.

“The Medical Association and the Ministry of Health may also reject the idea because it would dilute their work. For pharmacists to take on this role, they would need to undergo mandatory training courses provided by the association, with ongoing follow-up to ensure their skills are developed and up-to-date.” Participant 2

“The experience of pharmacists is not enough to manage chronic and complex cases because many of them can't even handle OTC medications properly, so how can they treat chronic cases?” Participant 3

“The primary challenge is the scientific knowledge of pharmacists, and they should stay updated. Additionally, institutional approval is required because no law allows pharmacists to prescribe treatments beyond OTC.” Participant 5

“The obstacles could lead to conflicts and problems with doctors because their role would be reduced. There might also be issues if a pharmacist makes a mistake and prescribes treatment for complicated cases without sufficient knowledge.” Participant 8

“There are several challenges: firstly, pharmacists may lack sufficient knowledge; secondly, the pharmacy design doesn't have a place for talking with patients like the clinic design, and thirdly, serious cases require thorough examination and investigation, which is limited in a pharmacy setting.” Participant 10

Theme 6: Requirements for implementation of independent prescribing

The final theme, which represents the largest component of this study, focuses on the key requirements for implementing independent prescribing. Drawing on the insights and perspectives of participating pharmacists, it is evident that several essential factors must be addressed to support the effective establishment of independent prescribing in Iraq. These include pharmacist competence, appropriate training, clear governance structures, and regulatory support. Accordingly, this theme is organized into the following key areas:

- A. Pharmacist competence.
- B. Resources and training required for implementing IP.
- C. Regulatory support to facilitate implementation.
- D. Institutional adoption of independent prescribing.
- E. Designation of a responsible authority for training and post-implementation monitoring of pharmacists.

Pharmacist competence

Pharmacist competence encompasses the skills, knowledge, and qualifications required for effective independent prescribing practice. Participating pharmacists emphasized that education and training are the most critical factors in developing this competence. This can be achieved through:

- Continuous professional development (CPD) to enhance knowledge and strengthen clinical skills.
- Advanced qualifications, with pharmacists involved in diagnosis holding credentials beyond a bachelor's degree, including specialized postgraduate training in pharmacy.

“Regarding the pharmacist's role, it's up to them to self-develop, expand their knowledge, and conduct further research.” Participant 4

“The most important thing is education, and also practices in hospitals, with a minimum of one year of practical experience. This could involve a 6-year study program or even a 2-year postgraduate program for recent graduates to enhance their skills and knowledge.” Participant 8

“I suggest providing additional courses in specialized disease areas, such as angina and others, during their studies. If IP is implemented initially, it should be limited to those with postgraduate certificates and studies. This could motivate pharmacists to pursue further studies, enabling them to enter this field.” Participant 3

Resources and training required for implementing independent prescribing

In addition to professional experience, the implementation of independent prescribing in Iraq would require further qualifications, including specialized education and access to appropriate resources. According to participating pharmacists, key training and resource requirements could include:

- Structured training programs delivered by the Iraqi Pharmacists' Syndicate.
- A dedicated postgraduate program in independent prescribing, potentially of 1 year's duration.
- Integration of relevant content into undergraduate pharmacy curricula to better prepare students for independent prescribing from the outset.

“Honestly, I'm not in a position to determine the specific resources and curricula they need. However, if the topic is more specialized in a particular area, the outcome would be better for both the pharmacist and the patient. This way, the pharmacist would have in-depth knowledge in a specific area, but I'm not aware of the relevant guidelines or resources. Certainly, professors at universities might have more experience in this area and know the correct approach to implement this project.” Participant 1

“I suggest that they undergo training, which the Pharmacists’ syndicate should provide. Additionally, if students are still in the process of graduating, we need to incorporate this topic into their curriculum to prepare them for the first step in this field.” Participant 2

“After graduation, pharmacists require a minimum of one year of training from the syndicate before they are qualified to enter this field.” Participant 3

“Through workshops, training courses, and lectures provided by pharmacists from the Ministry or the Union.” Participant 3

“Firstly, obtaining a high-ranking degree and certification is essential, and not everyone can attain it. Higher education institutions can also play a role in preparing and qualifying pharmacists through specific options, such as clinical pharmacy programs.” Participant 10

Regulatory support to facilitate implementation

To successfully implement independent prescribing in Iraq, support and facilitation from the Ministry of Health and the Pharmacists’ Syndicate are essential to address potential barriers, including resistance from physicians. Based on participants’ perspectives, potential facilitation strategies include:

1. Promoting stronger collaboration and professional relationships between physicians and pharmacists.
2. Developing and submitting a formal proposal to the Iraqi Ministry of Health to support the implementation of independent prescribing.

“With regards to the concerns of the doctors, we can address the issue by developing solutions and collaboration with the syndicate of the Pharmacists and the medical association. For example, when patients have non-doctor’s visit diseases, pharmacists can treat them, so there’s coordination between them.” Participant 2

“Through dialogue with the syndicate of pharmacists, if this proposal is to be reported to the Ministry, there will be no connotation-making issue in the actual implementation, and we can execute it with little difficulty. In addition, there will be a joint working process between medical and pharmacy personnel to prevent or reduce the likelihood of conflicts in the future.” Participant 6

“The solutions require the Ministry or pharmacists’ syndicate to take the lead in promoting this practice and establishing a system to distinguish pharmacies that meet the requirements. This could involve a scoring system based on periodic assessments, where successful pharmacies would receive certification and be authorized to provide services. Additionally, the second aspect is the design of the pharmacy with a specific area,” Participant 10

D. Institutional adoption of independent prescribing

Once a commitment to independent prescribing is established, the next crucial step is formal adoption. The majority of participating pharmacists agreed that the Iraqi Pharmacists’ Syndicate is best positioned to oversee this process. However, some suggested that the Ministry of Health or another relevant government body may be more appropriate to take on this role.

“In my opinion, the Pharmacist’s syndicate should be responsible for adopting this project,” Participant 2

“A collaboration between the Pharmacists’ syndicate and the Medical Association is necessary, given that pharmacists are expanding into areas traditionally dominated by doctors, and thus coordination between the two professions is essential.” Participant 3

“The Pharmacists’ syndicate communicates with the Ministry of Health, and a mutual agreement is obtained from both sides.” Participant 5

“It could be the Pharmacists’ syndicate or a higher government authority overseeing the Pharmacists’ syndicate,” Participant 6

“The Ministry of Health, and in most cases, they may not agree with this decision because most of them are doctors.” Participant 8

Designation of a responsible authority for training and post-implementation monitoring of pharmacists

Following the assessment of feasibility and the formal adoption of independent prescribing, supported by appropriate legislation, the final critical step is the organization and ongoing monitoring of pharmacists in practice. Effective oversight would be essential for evaluating outcomes and ensuring clear accountability. Accordingly, participants were asked which body should be responsible for monitoring, training, and regulating this practice post-implementation. Their responses identified two main candidates:

- The Ministry of Health
- The Syndicate of Iraqi Pharmacists

“Education is certainly the responsibility of colleges, but the Pharmacists’ Syndicate would be in charge of training, as after graduation, the pharmacist joins the union. A combination could also be developed between the Medical Association and the Pharmacists’ Syndicate.” Participant 3

“If it’s legally recognized, then the Ministry of Health would definitely be responsible, which would be a potential outcome. [They can produce licenses] for practicing

this occupation, like the clinical pharmacy program, that the Ministry of Health could regulate.” Participant 4

“Some entities have linked themselves to the Ministry of Health or the Syndicate, but it’s extremely difficult to monitor all pharmacies and pharmacists. It would fall on whoever takes up this topic, and he would decide the cases that the pharmacists can diagnose and treat.” Participant 6

In each hospital, the Ministry decides that a few of its pharmacists are rotated from department to department to attend training. In terms of the body that oversees them, they could be through periodic assessment courses or regular inspection committees.” Participant 7

Discussion

This qualitative study highlights the enthusiasm of community pharmacists for expanding their professional roles to include independent prescribing, alongside their pragmatic understanding of its implementation and associated challenges.

Iraqi community pharmacists demonstrated a strong interest in independent prescribing as a means of improving patient care. This aligns with global trends supporting expanded pharmacist roles to enhance access to cost-effective and efficient healthcare (Abd-ul Munaf and Al-Hamadani 2024). Participants identified several potential patient benefits, particularly improved cost-effectiveness and time efficiency, which are key considerations in optimizing healthcare delivery. Pharmacists were also perceived as highly accessible healthcare providers, often offering consultations free of charge, thereby reducing both time and financial burdens on patients. In addition, participants suggested that independent prescribing could help alleviate pressures on overstretched healthcare services, including public clinics and private practices. These findings are consistent with existing literature, which supports the role of independent prescribing in improving patient outcomes and reducing workload pressures in high-demand clinical settings (Poh et al. 2018).

While respondents supported independent prescribing, they also highlighted significant gaps in clinical training and practice. Some noted that recent graduates have received limited practical training, alongside an increasing emphasis on pharmaceutical marketing within pharmacy education. Participants therefore called for improvements to the curriculum and stronger regulatory oversight to address these concerns. Existing literature on independent prescribing reinforces the importance of robust clinical education and continuous professional development for safe and effective practice (Przymuszała et al. 2023; Naja et al. 2024). Pharmacists' preference for managing uncomplicated conditions, coupled with their caution regarding more complex cases, reflects a realistic appraisal of their current competencies.

Participants identified the lack of clear regulatory guidance as a major barrier to the implementation of independent prescribing. They emphasized the need for collaboration between the Ministry of Health and the Iraqi Pharmacists' Syndicate to establish clear frameworks defining scope of practice, legal protections, and professional responsibilities. Practical challenges were also highlighted, including the absence of private consultation areas within pharmacies and limited access to laboratory results. These infrastructure limitations underscore the need for system-level support to enable safe and effective clinical decision-making at scale.

Even within well-established healthcare systems, several barriers to independent prescribing persist. These include limited time for safe prescribing, inadequate funding, restricted access to patient information, and concerns related to professional indemnity (Alexander et al. 2025). There is also evidence suggesting that current training does not sufficiently prepare pharmacists for complex clinical decision-making, highlighting the need for practice-based, case-based education, as well as structured clinical supervision and mentorship (Davies et al. 2024; Alexander et al. 2025). Successful implementation further depends on effective integration within multidisciplinary teams and a clear understanding of pharmacists' roles in relation to other healthcare professionals (Hassan et al. 2025). Participants also anticipated potential resistance from physicians to the expansion of pharmacists' roles, a challenge that has been documented in the international literature (Tahaineh et al. 2019). To support collaborative practice, the development of clear regulatory frameworks, co-produced by pharmacy and medical bodies, is essential.

These challenges faced by Iraqi pharmacists reflect broader issues within the country's healthcare system. The widespread, unregulated dispensing of prescription-only drugs has been linked to the absence of robust pharmaceutical regulatory frameworks and limited governmental oversight and scrutiny (Agomo et al. 2018). Cultural barriers, such as reluctance to sign formal documentation, may also constrain the development of formal clinical roles (Mikhael et al. 2024). Similar challenges have been reported in neighboring countries. For example, in Jordan, pharmacists demonstrated positive attitudes toward prescribing; however, insufficient training in patient assessment and diagnosis was identified as a key barrier (Mhailan et al. 2022). A key lesson from these contexts is that professional enthusiasm must be supported by strong foundational clinical training and an enabling regulatory environment to ensure safe and effective role expansion.

In the United Arab Emirates (UAE), pharmacists operate within a more formalized regulatory framework, with clearly defined prescribing and dispensing practices. However, several challenges remain, including limited protected time, minimal incentives, restricted access to patient records, and some concerns regarding physician support (Sadeq et al. 2022). Although many pharmacists in the UAE feel confident managing minor conditions,

they report needing additional support when dealing with chronic diseases, as well as improvements in consultation processes. Despite these challenges, the high level of professional willingness to expand clinical roles suggests that the UAE could serve as a regional model for the development of pharmacist-led practice.

Saudi Arabia presents a contrasting case. While pharmacists demonstrate a high level of readiness to engage in prescribing, with more than 87% supporting prescribing rights, implementation remains constrained by the absence of a formal legal framework, insufficient clinical training, and notable resistance from physicians (Abutaleb 2025). Many pharmacists advocate for the introduction of postgraduate education and competency-based assessments to ensure safe practice. Implementation is further challenged by the lack of standardized prescribing pathways and limited interprofessional collaboration (Ajabnoor and Cooper 2020). Despite these barriers, Saudi pharmacists show strong enthusiasm for reform, and policy developments aligned with international models could help unlock their potential to enhance healthcare delivery.

Limitations of the study

This study has several limitations. The sample was predominantly male (nine out of 10 participants), which introduces the potential for gender bias and may limit the diversity of perspectives captured. As a qualitative study with a small purposive sample, the findings provide rich contextual insights but are not generalizable to the wider population of community pharmacists in Iraq. Furthermore, clinical pharmacists, who often have greater exposure to hospital-based prescribing practices and may be more prepared for independent prescribing, were not included. Their perspectives could have provided valuable comparative insights. Future research should aim for more balanced gender representation and include pharmacists from a broader range of practice settings to better inform the development of this evolving professional role.

Conclusion

Community pharmacists in Iraq are generally optimistic about independent prescribing, recognizing its potential to improve patient outcomes and enhance healthcare efficiency. However, realizing this potential depends on overcoming several key challenges, including (i) strengthening pharmacist training, (ii) fostering interprofessional collaboration, and, most importantly, (iii) establishing robust regulatory and educational frameworks. Addressing these challenges will require coordinated efforts from the Iraqi Ministry of Health, the Pharmacists' Syndicate, and the academic community to develop structured training pathways, implement enabling legislation, and create a collaborative practice environment. Such efforts are essential to sup-

port the safe and effective integration of independent prescribing into pharmacy practice and to advance patient care in Iraq.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: The study was approved by the Research Ethical Committee of the University of Baghdad, College of Pharmacy (Approval Number: RECAUBCP 1562024112R).

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, investigation, and manuscript preparation: Al-Hamadani Fadya Y., Jasim AL, Fawzi HA. Supervision: Fawzi HA, Alhamdani Faaiz Y. Statistical analysis and review of final results: Al-Hamadani Fadya Y., Jasim AL, Fawzi HA. Manuscript review and editing: Al-Hamadani Fadya Y., Jasim AL, Saihood AH, Jawad SAK, Jabbar MM, Fawzi HA, Alhamdani Faaiz Y. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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